

Equations for Spacelike Biharmonic General Helices with Timelike Normal According to Bishop Frame in The Lorentzian Group of Rigid Motions $\mathbb{E}(1, 1)$

Talat KÖRPINAR and Essin TURHAN

(Fırat University, Department of Mathematics 23119, Elazığ, Turkey)

E-mail: talatkorpınar@gmail.com, essin.turhan@gmail.com

Abstract: In this paper, we study spacelike biharmonic general helices according to Bishop frame in the Lorentzian group of rigid motions $\mathbb{E}(1, 1)$. We characterize the spacelike biharmonic general helices in terms of their curvatures in the Lorentzian group of rigid motions $\mathbb{E}(1, 1)$.

Key Words: Biharmonic curve, bienergy, bitension field, bishop frame, rigid motion.

AMS(2010): 53C41, 53A10

§1. Introduction

A helix, sometimes also called a coil, is a curve for which the tangent makes a constant angle with a fixed line. The shortest path between two points on a cylinder (one not directly above the other) is a fractional turn of a helix, as can be seen by cutting the cylinder along one of its sides, flattening it out, and noting that a straight line connecting the points becomes helical upon re-wrapping. It is for this reason that squirrels chasing one another up and around tree trunks follow helical paths.

Helices can be either right-handed or left-handed. With the line of sight along the helix's axis, if a clockwise screwing motion moves the helix away from the observer, then it is called a right-handed helix; if towards the observer then it is a left-handed helix. Handedness (or chirality) is a property of the helix, not of the perspective: a right-handed helix cannot be turned or flipped to look like a left-handed one unless it is viewed in a mirror, and vice versa.

Most hardware screw threads are right-handed helices. The alpha helix in biology as well as the A and B forms of DNA are also right-handed helices. The Z form of DNA is left-handed.

The pitch of a helix is the width of one complete helix turn, measured parallel to the axis of the helix. A double helix consists of two (typically congruent) helices with the same axis, differing by a translation along the axis.

The notions of harmonic and biharmonic maps between Riemannian manifolds have been introduced by J. Eells and J.H. Sampson (see [4]).

¹Received August 19, 2011. Accepted February 25, 2012.

A smooth map $\phi : N \longrightarrow M$ is said to be biharmonic if it is a critical point of the bienergy functional:

$$E_2(\phi) = \int_N \frac{1}{2} |\mathcal{T}(\phi)|^2 dv_h,$$

where $\mathcal{T}(\phi) := \text{tr} \nabla^\phi d\phi$ is the tension field of ϕ

The Euler–Lagrange equation of the bienergy is given by $\mathcal{T}_2(\phi) = 0$. Here the section $\mathcal{T}_2(\phi)$ is defined by

$$\mathcal{T}_2(\phi) = -\Delta_\phi \mathcal{T}(\phi) + \text{tr} R(\mathcal{T}(\phi), d\phi) d\phi, \quad (1.1)$$

and called the bitension field of ϕ . Non-harmonic biharmonic maps are called proper biharmonic maps.

In this paper, we study spacelike biharmonic general helices according to Bishop frame in the Lorentzian group of rigid motions $\mathbb{E}(1, 1)$. We characterize the spacelike biharmonic general helices in terms of their curvatures in the Lorentzian group of rigid motions $\mathbb{E}(1, 1)$. Finally, we obtain parametric equations of spacelike biharmonic general helices according to Bishop frame in the Lorentzian group of rigid motions $\mathbb{E}(1, 1)$.

§2. Preliminaries

Let $\mathbb{E}(1, 1)$ be the group of rigid motions of Euclidean 2-space. This consists of all matrices of the form

$$\begin{pmatrix} \cosh x & \sinh x & y \\ \sinh x & \cosh x & z \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Topologically, $\mathbb{E}(1, 1)$ is diffeomorphic to \mathbb{R}^3 under the map

$$\mathbb{E}(1, 1) \longrightarrow \mathbb{R}^3 : \begin{pmatrix} \cosh x & \sinh x & y \\ \sinh x & \cosh x & z \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \longrightarrow (x, y, z),$$

It's Lie algebra has a basis consisting of

$$\mathbf{X}_1 = \frac{\partial}{\partial x}, \quad \mathbf{X}_2 = \cosh x \frac{\partial}{\partial y} + \sinh x \frac{\partial}{\partial z}, \quad \mathbf{X}_3 = \sinh x \frac{\partial}{\partial y} + \cosh x \frac{\partial}{\partial z},$$

for which

$$[\mathbf{X}_1, \mathbf{X}_2] = \mathbf{X}_3, \quad [\mathbf{X}_2, \mathbf{X}_3] = 0, \quad [\mathbf{X}_1, \mathbf{X}_3] = \mathbf{X}_2.$$

Put

$$x^1 = x, \quad x^2 = \frac{1}{2}(y+z), \quad x^3 = \frac{1}{2}(y-z).$$

Then, we get

$$\mathbf{X}_1 = \frac{\partial}{\partial x^1}, \quad \mathbf{X}_2 = \frac{1}{2} \left(e^{x^1} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^2} + e^{-x^1} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^3} \right), \quad \mathbf{X}_3 = \frac{1}{2} \left(e^{x^1} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^2} - e^{-x^1} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^3} \right). \quad (2.1)$$

The bracket relations are

$$[\mathbf{X}_1, \mathbf{X}_2] = \mathbf{X}_3, \quad [\mathbf{X}_2, \mathbf{X}_3] = 0, \quad [\mathbf{X}_1, \mathbf{X}_3] = \mathbf{X}_2. \quad (2.2)$$

We consider left-invariant Lorentzian metrics which has a pseudo-orthonormal basis $\{\mathbf{X}_1, \mathbf{X}_2, \mathbf{X}_3\}$. We consider left-invariant Lorentzian metric [10], given by

$$g = -(dx^1)^2 + \left(e^{-x^1} dx^2 + e^{x^1} dx^3\right)^2 + \left(e^{-x^1} dx^2 - e^{x^1} dx^3\right)^2, \quad (2.3)$$

where

$$g(\mathbf{X}_1, \mathbf{X}_1) = -1, \quad g(\mathbf{X}_2, \mathbf{X}_2) = g(\mathbf{X}_3, \mathbf{X}_3) = 1. \quad (2.4)$$

Let coframe of our frame be defined by

$$\theta^1 = dx^1, \quad \theta^2 = e^{-x^1} dx^2 + e^{x^1} dx^3, \quad \theta^3 = e^{-x^1} dx^2 - e^{x^1} dx^3.$$

Proposition 2.1 *For the covariant derivatives of the Levi-Civita connection of the left-invariant metric g , defined above the following is true:*

$$\nabla = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\mathbf{X}_3 & 0 & -\mathbf{X}_1 \\ -\mathbf{X}_2 & -\mathbf{X}_1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.5)$$

where the (i, j) -element in the table above equals $\nabla_{\mathbf{X}_i} \mathbf{X}_j$ for our basis

$$\{\mathbf{X}_k, k = 1, 2, 3\} = \{\mathbf{X}_1, \mathbf{X}_2, \mathbf{X}_3\}.$$

§3. Spacelike Biharmonic General Helices with Timelike Normal According to Bishop Frame in the Lorentzian Group of Rigid Motions $\mathbb{E}(1, 1)$

Let $\gamma : I \rightarrow \mathbb{E}(1, 1)$ be a non geodesic spacelike curve on the $\mathbb{E}(1, 1)$ parametrized by arc length.

Let $\{\mathbf{T}, \mathbf{N}, \mathbf{B}\}$ be the Frenet frame fields tangent to the $\mathbb{E}(1, 1)$ along γ defined as follows:

\mathbf{T} is the unit vector field γ' tangent to γ , \mathbf{N} is the unit vector field in the direction of $\nabla_{\mathbf{T}} \mathbf{T}$ (normal to γ), and \mathbf{B} is chosen so that $\{\mathbf{T}, \mathbf{N}, \mathbf{B}\}$ is a positively oriented orthonormal basis. Then, we have the following Frenet formulas:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_{\mathbf{T}} \mathbf{T} &= \kappa \mathbf{N}, \\ \nabla_{\mathbf{T}} \mathbf{N} &= \kappa \mathbf{T} + \tau \mathbf{B}, \\ \nabla_{\mathbf{T}} \mathbf{B} &= \tau \mathbf{N}, \end{aligned}$$

where κ is the curvature of γ and τ is its torsion and

$$\begin{aligned} g(\mathbf{T}, \mathbf{T}) &= 1, \quad g(\mathbf{N}, \mathbf{N}) = -1, \quad g(\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{B}) = 1, \\ g(\mathbf{T}, \mathbf{N}) &= g(\mathbf{T}, \mathbf{B}) = g(\mathbf{N}, \mathbf{B}) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

The Bishop frame or parallel transport frame is an alternative approach to defining a moving frame that is well defined even when the curve has vanishing second derivative. The Bishop frame is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}\nabla_{\mathbf{T}}\mathbf{T} &= k_1\mathbf{M}_1 - k_2\mathbf{M}_2, \\ \nabla_{\mathbf{T}}\mathbf{M}_1 &= k_1\mathbf{T}, \\ \nabla_{\mathbf{T}}\mathbf{M}_2 &= k_2\mathbf{T},\end{aligned}\tag{3.1}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}g(\mathbf{T}, \mathbf{T}) &= 1, \quad g(\mathbf{M}_1, \mathbf{M}_1) = -1, \quad g(\mathbf{M}_2, \mathbf{M}_2) = 1, \\ g(\mathbf{T}, \mathbf{M}_1) &= g(\mathbf{T}, \mathbf{M}_2) = g(\mathbf{M}_1, \mathbf{M}_2) = 0.\end{aligned}\tag{3.2}$$

Here, we shall call the set $\{\mathbf{T}, \mathbf{M}_1, \mathbf{M}_2\}$ as Bishop trihedra, k_1 and k_2 as Bishop curvatures and $\tau(s) = \psi'(s)$, $\kappa(s) = \sqrt{|k_2^2 - k_1^2|}$. Thus, Bishop curvatures are defined by

$$\begin{aligned}k_1 &= \kappa(s) \sinh \psi(s), \\ k_2 &= \kappa(s) \cosh \psi(s).\end{aligned}$$

With respect to the orthonormal basis $\{\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \mathbf{e}_3\}$ we can write

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{T} &= T^1\mathbf{e}_1 + T^2\mathbf{e}_2 + T^3\mathbf{e}_3, \\ \mathbf{M}_1 &= M_1^1\mathbf{e}_1 + M_1^2\mathbf{e}_2 + M_1^3\mathbf{e}_3, \\ \mathbf{M}_2 &= M_2^1\mathbf{e}_1 + M_2^2\mathbf{e}_2 + M_2^3\mathbf{e}_3.\end{aligned}\tag{3.3}$$

Theorem 3.1 $\gamma : I \longrightarrow \mathbb{E}(1, 1)$ is a spacelike biharmonic curve with Bishop frame if and only if

$$\begin{aligned}k_1^2 - k_2^2 &= \text{constant} = C \neq 0, \\ k_1'' + Ck_1 &= -k_1 \left[1 + 2(M_2^1)^2 \right] + 2k_2 M_1^1 M_2^1, \\ k_2'' + Ck_2 &= -2k_1 M_1^1 M_2^1 - k_2 \left[-1 + 2(M_1^1)^2 \right].\end{aligned}\tag{3.4}$$

Definition 3.2 A regular spacelike curve $\gamma : I \longrightarrow \mathbb{E}(1, 1)$ is called a general helix provided the spacelike unit vector \mathbf{T} of the curve γ has constant angle θ with some fixed timelike unit vector u , that is

$$g(\mathbf{T}(s), u) = \cosh \varphi \text{ for all } s \in I.\tag{3.5}$$

Theorem 3.4 Let $\gamma : I \longrightarrow \mathbb{E}(1, 1)$ is a non geodesic spacelike biharmonic general helix with timelike normal in the Lorentzian group of rigid motions $\mathbb{E}(1, 1)$. Then, the parametric equations

of γ are

$$\begin{aligned} x^1(s) &= \cosh \wp s + C_1, \\ x^2(s) &= \frac{\sqrt{1 + \cosh^2 \wp} e^{\cosh \wp s + C_1}}{2 \cosh \wp} [\cos s + \sin s] + C_2, \\ x^3(s) &= \frac{\sqrt{1 + \cosh^2 \wp} e^{-\cosh \wp s - C_1}}{2 \cosh \wp} [\cos s - \sin s] + C_3, \end{aligned} \quad (3.6)$$

where C_1, C_2, C_3 are constants of integration.

Proof Using (3.1) and (3.5) we have above system. □

Fig.1

References

- [1] K.Arslan, R.Ezentas, C.Murathan and T.Sasahara, Biharmonic submanifolds 3-dimensional (κ, μ) -manifolds, *Internat. J. Math. Sci.*, 22 (2005), 3575-3586.
- [2] L.R.Bishop, There is more than one way to frame a curve, *Amer. Math. Monthly*, 82 (3) (1975) 246-251.
- [3] M.P.Carmo, *Differential Geometry of Curves and Surfaces*, Pearson Education, 1976.
- [4] J.Eells and J.H.Sampson, Harmonic mappings of Riemannian manifolds, *Amer. J. Math.*, 86 (1964), 109-160.
- [5] G.Y.Jiang, 2-harmonic isometric immersions between Riemannian manifolds, *Chinese Ann. Math. Ser. A* 7(2) (1986), 130-144.
- [6] K.İlarslan and Ö.Boyacıoğlu, Position vectors of a timelike and a null helix in Minkowski 3-space, *Chaos Solitons Fractals*, 38 (2008), 1383-1389.
- [7] T.Körpınar, E.Turhan, On Horizontal Biharmonic Curves In The Heisenberg Group $Heis^3$, *Arab. J. Sci. Eng. Sect. A Sci.* 35 (1) (2010), 79-85.

- [9] W.Kuhnel, *Differential Geometry, Curves-Surfaces-Manifolds*, Braunschweig, Wiesbaden, 1999.
- [10] K.Onda, Lorentz Ricci Solitons on 3-dimensional Lie groups, *Geom Dedicata*, 147 (1) (2010), 313-322.
- [11] E.Turhan and T.Körpınar, On characterization of timelike horizontal biharmonic curves in the Lorentzian Heisenberg Group $heis^3$, *Zeitschrift für Naturforschung A- A Journal of Physical Sciences*, 65a (2010), 641-648.
- [12] E.Turhan, and T.Körpınar, Biharmonic slant helices according to bishop frame in E^3 , *International Journal of Mathematical Combinatorics*, 3 (2010), 64-68.
- [13] S.Yilmaz and M.Turgut, On the differential geometry of the curves in Minkowski spacetime I, *Int. J. Contemp. Math. Sciences*, 3 (2008),1343-1349.